

Computing Earth: what sort of thing is a computable planet?

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Abstract: Earth is increasingly staged as a computable object: an entity that can be known, simulated, and governed through computational infrastructures. Synthesising philosophy of technology and critical cultural analysis, this article argues that computable Earths are best understood as the operational outcome of what Gilbert Simondon called technical ensembles. We propose that a computable planet is an operational object made governable by ensembles that stabilise addressability (what can be named and queried), actionability (what can be processed and approximated), and intervention (what outputs count as grounds for decision). Using the European Commission's Destination Earth as a diagnostic case, we show how platform entry points and data backbones organise interoperability and access, while twin engines orchestrate simulation and machine-learning extensions to produce outputs aligned with governance decisions. Incomputability appears in practice as remainder: what cannot be fully resolved at planetary scale and must be handled through approximation, proxy, and uncertainty management. Machine learning intensifies this process, shifting the terms on which outputs become traceable, interpretable, and actionable. By positioning computability as an ensemble achievement rather than a totalising representation, we clarify how Earth is made governable—and what becomes excluded, externalised, or treated as acceptable loss in the process.

Keywords: computability, Destination Earth, planetary computation, climate modelling, digital twins, computation

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Earth is increasingly staged as a computable object: an entity that can be known, simulated, and governed through computational infrastructures. This staging is visible in different ways across corporate initiatives such as Microsoft's Planetary Computer and Nvidia's Earth-2, in intergovernmental programs such as the European Commission's Destination Earth and Digital Twin of the Ocean, and in long-standing Earth systems modelling frameworks—general

circulation and coupled models—central to climate knowledge production and institutions such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). These initiatives increasingly seek to make Earth systems operable by assembling data sources, modelling regimes, and interfaces in ways that yield actionable projections, test out scenarios, and support governance and even automate decision-making. Understanding how this happens and what it means for knowledge and decision infrastructures requires attending to the specific architectures through which “Earth” is constituted as computable and thus governable within prevailing institutional and political logics.

This article proposes that computable Earths be understood as the operational outcome of technical ensembles. By “ensemble” we mean linked sociotechnical entities—including models, compute infrastructures, standards, interfaces, and organisational arrangements—that must be coordinated to maintain the functioning of planetary computation. In this sense, the computable planet is produced through relations: between climate models and observational data; between simulation engines and machine-learning components; between data lakes, APIs, and user-facing dashboards; and between these technical arrangements and the institutions that authorise their use. Treating the computable planet as an ensemble shifts emphasis away from computation as representation and toward the question of how operativity is assembled and sustained, bringing into view forms and processes of authority and intervention (Richardson and Munster 2023). It also foregrounds incomputability as a limit condition: a managed remainder that ensembles variously render into probabilities, treat as noise, or defer and externalise. We argue that a computable planet is an operational object: a planet made actionable by technical ensembles that stabilise addressability (what can be named and queried), actionability (what can be processed and approximated), and intervention (what outputs count as grounds for decision).

Our central proposition is that the object-ness of contemporary planetary computation is undergoing a marked transformation as machine learning is inserted into Earth sensing, modelling, and forecasting regimes. Jennifer Gabrys’s *Program Earth* (2016) remains the critical, foundational account of how environments become computational through sensing technologies, data practices, and the programmability of distributed systems. For Gabrys, programmability is an expansive concept that exceeds computation as such to account for how

environments are generated across devices, sensors, people, practices, and so on (2016, p. 9-11). While rightly influential, it was published just as the machine learning era began to gather force, and as such it primarily addresses a paradigm that centres data (its collection, values, limitations, and so on) rather than *computation* as such, and particularly deep learning models, in which processing takes place in the inscrutable layers of neural networks and its latent spaces. It also stems from an era in which climate and Earth systems science models were becoming increasingly complex and interoperable, but in which computation's role remained primarily in the crunching of ever more complicated formula applied to ever expanding statistic datasets. In the decade since, Earth computation has undergone a step change in which climate and earth systems scientists are now using machine learning techniques to smooth and gap-fill data or to undertake novel pattern analysis that enables alternative predictive tools to the traditional, observation-centred models (National Academy of Sciences 2022). This increasing uptake of machine learning in climate and Earth systems science—and, more dramatically, in corporate and intergovernmental digital twin platforms—has intensified a shift from programmability toward computability as a distinctive regime of planetary knowledge-making.

Computability does not refer merely to the existence of code, the presence of data, or the digital processing of numbers, but to the conditions and techniques under which Earth systems can be rendered addressable and actionable at scale. As machine learning takes hold, the techniques that hold Earth computing together shift towards probabilistic projections, surrogate modelling, downscaling and gap-filling, and forms of approximation that frequently exceed older assumptions of traceable hierarchy and stable translation between equations, numerical schemes, and predictions. These techniques and the institutional and market conditions in which they take place are not politically neutral, freighted as they are with determinations of inclusion and exclusion, epistemic priorities, dataset interoperability, and compute availability. Nor are they evenly adopted, with climate and Earth systems sciences tending to take a much more cautious view of machine learning computation in contrast to the fulsome embrace of corporate and hybrid systems. Machine learning changes how uncertainty is handled, how resolution and scale are produced, and – crucially – how outputs orient towards management decisions, whether at the micro or macro scales. This shift towards machine learning computation, with its reliance on

compression and hidden layers, brings with it new challenges of accountability, legitimacy, and the distribution of risks and benefits.

To grapple with how Earth becomes computable, we synthesise approaches to computability and its value systems from media theory, science and technology studies, and critical cultural theories of computation. In what follows, we combine conceptual analysis of technicity and computability with close reading of published technical and institutional descriptions of Earth modelling platforms and modelling debates, treating these materials as evidence of how planetary computation is assembled as an operational object. Rather than provide an extensive empirical account of Earth as computable, our aim is to propose an analytical framework for treating planetary computation as an object of analysis. To that end, we use Destination Earth as a concrete example of how a computable planet is composed from linked architectures to produce forms of addressability and action. We locate Destination Earth as both a continuation and departure point from longstanding efforts to compute Earth, since most (if not all) contemporary Earth computation initiatives depend upon scientific models refined over decades of physical observation and simulation. Our aim is to specify what sort of object the computable planet is when understood as an ensemble whose operativity must be continually produced, stabilised, and authorised. We focus on the infrastructural and epistemic conditions that make the planet computable in the first place: the operational architectures through which “Earth” becomes an object of computation and governance, and the forms of indeterminacy and incomputability that persist within and against those architectures. By positioning computability as an ensemble achievement rather than a totalising representation, we provide a framework for analysing how planetary computation reorders knowledge and action, and why the question of the computable planet is inseparable from the values that shape what can be known, modelled, and managed.¹

¹ This aspect of questioning planetary computability as a totality is also an important topic in art and research about aesthetic imaginaries of machinic landscapes. See theme issue "Machinic Visions of the Planetary" in *Media+Environment* (2023), edited by Lila-Lee Morrison, Dominique Routhier, Kathrin Maurer. See also Maurer's work on drone sensing the earth surface in an agricultural and artistic context: Kathrin Maurer, *The Sensorium of the Drone and Communities* (2023).

Ensembles for computing the planet are distinctive from other technical ensembles in what they are built to do: stabilise Earth systems as decision-relevant objects within predictive governance regimes. To do this, they must translate across scales—producing local resolutions of analysis from global dynamics—and they must operationalise limits by converting incomputable complexity into administrable uncertainty so outputs can circulate as legitimate grounds for action. In doing so, they reconfigure the epistemic contract of modelling: what counts as a traceable prediction, who can act on it, and under what conditions of legitimacy. At the same time, the material infrastructures that sustain this operativity are not externalities in the usual sense but part of the planetary transformation the models seek to comprehend and manage. Computable planes are ensembles built to turn Earth into a governable object, stabilising prediction within decision-making across state, corporate, and intergovernmental sites.

Efforts to conceptualise the “planetary” have proliferated across disciplines as thinkers reckon with Anthropocene scale, complexity, and unevenness (Chakrabarty 2021; Hui 2024; Latour 2017; Likavčan 2019; Morton 2013). Despite their differences, these projects share a wager that “the planetary” exceeds familiar epistemic frames while demanding new forms of intelligibility and action, and they converge on a problem of objecthood: how Earth’s multiplicity becomes graspable as a coherent object without collapsing what exceeds grasp into manageable abstraction. This problem increasingly meets contemporary computational efforts to make Earth systems not only knowable but operable. Benjamin Bratton is emblematic in drawing the planet into computational reason, but the convergence is broader: across science, capital, security, and governance, the “planetary” becomes a target (Chow 2006) to be stabilised as an actionable object. As Guyatri Spivak (2015) cautions, theory can itself enclose what resists being tamed, while Orit Halpern (2021) traces how “smartness” extends enclosure into infrastructures promising automated planetary intelligence via evolving practices of large-scale experiment (Halpern and Mitchell 2026). Our aim is to shift from planetary theory as a contest over representations to the question of how “the planetary” is operationalised computationally. Our wager that attending to the technoscientific ensembles that render Earth addressable, actionable, and governable will expose the arrangements, values, and infrastructures through which specific versions of the planetary are made to count within planning, management, and policy contexts.

In what follows, we begin by setting out an approach to computation via Gilbert Simondon’s philosophy of technical ensembles, before tracing the longer history of the computational model of Earth. From there, we attend to how the European Commission’s Destination Earth platform embodies the operative ambitions of new computing regimes, before considering in detail how the incomputable challenges the governance logics of Earth computation.

Computable Ensembles

The promise of a “computable” planet depends on the capacity to make Earth systems operable and actionable: to aggregate heterogeneous observations and models, align them through standards and interfaces, and produce outputs that can circulate as decision-relevant knowledge. Destination Earth is exemplary in this respect, as we show below. Such initiatives are underpinned by the operationalisation of Earth systems, events, and environments through meta-organising sociotechnical arrangements. Understanding computable Earths therefore requires thinking “computability” and “objecthood” together. A computable planet is not a self-identical representation (a Borges-like 1:1 map), but an object whose objecthood obtains through the coordination of models, datasets, compute infrastructures, and institutions. This coordination is never static for long, so the computable ensemble must be continuously stabilised to maintain its operativity. Sustaining the ensemble requires continually negotiating inclusions and exclusions. On a programmatic level, computable ensembles require selecting what *will* be computed from the broad terrain of what *can*.

Thinking the computable planet through Gilbert Simondon’s account of technical beings—from technical elements to technical individuals and ensembles—brings contingency, uncertainty, and becoming into view. Simondon’s emphasis on operation (rather than fixed qualities) helps disrupt what Deleuze and Guattari (1987) call overcoding: the imposition of a sovereign schema that claims to organise heterogeneous becomings, smoothing contingency into a legible and governable order. This impulse is visible in projects that promise a seamless digital twin of Earth. A Simondonian orientation also aligns with Adrian Mackenzie’s (2005) critique of “the Technological” as a pre-given explanatory grid, emphasising instead technical objects as events and processes whose determinations exceed any single ordering framework. As Aurora Hoel

(2020) notes, Simondon’s *fonctionner* can be translated not only as “to function,” but as “to operate.” Read this way, technical beings are defined by the operations that dynamise them, and by the relations through which they maintain their capacity to operate—relations that include human operators, institutions, and milieus. It is this latter aspect that concerns us here, captured in Simondon’s contrast between structure and operation: “defining structures based on the operations that dynamize them, instead of knowing by defining operations based on the structures between which they are carried out” (Hoel 2020).

If we treat planetary computation projects as Simondonian technical beings, they appear less as finished “replicas” of Earth than as contingent processes of individuation. For Simondon, technical objects are not defined by fixed qualities but by operations that hold together heterogeneous elements while retaining “margins of indeterminacy”—such that “the machine endowed with a high degree of technicity is an open machine” (2017, 17). His example of the computer is instructive: a device often taken to perform a single function (calculation) nevertheless remains open to other operations, including symbolic translation and transformation (Simondon 2017, 17). Planetary computation projects intensify this openness. Their objecthood does not reside in a unified representation of Earth so much as in the continual coordination of interdependent algorithms and models, APIs that call up disparate Earth-system datasets, and cloud infrastructures that require ongoing orchestration across distributed computational arrays. Understood in operative terms, the computable planet demands attention to both the diagrammatics that organise ensembles and the material conditions that sustain them (including compute, power, and cooling). The point is not a smooth evolution from one purpose to another, but a metastable recomposition of operations, relations, and milieus.

Earth computing projects share some qualities of what Yuk Hui calls the “digital object” (2016): objects composed of data and metadata, regulated by schemas, and constituted within a digital milieu of protocols, standards, parameters, and algorithms. Hui’s account is useful insofar as it names the infrastructural conditions—schemas, standards, protocols—through which objects become networkable and actionable. Our emphasis, however, is on computation and operativity rather than digitality as such. Computation is not reducible to the digital, and computability depends on material conditions from which it cannot be extricated. In Simondon’s terms, the

computer is a technical being not primarily because it automates tasks, but because it enables *transduction* across registers of information: the conversion of energy and form from one domain to another (for instance, transducing images to numbers and back). This capacity for transduction is also a defining feature of the shift from intentional *programmability* (per Gabrys) to *computability*, since it points to the insistent assembling of components (data pipelines, training and inference processes, output formats) into ever-more ambitious ensembles. Transduction is not translation; it entails instability and excess, with conversions that can perturb the domains they traverse. In planetary computation, this matters because the “planet” is not simply digitised; it is continually transduced across observational systems, numerical models, machine-learning components, interfaces, and institutional decision loops. These projects therefore appear less as discrete objects than as technical ensembles whose operativity must be maintained across multiple registers and milieus to deliver on their promises of Earth systems management.

Computable ensembles attempt to render Earth into an operational regime that can not only be known but increasingly managed through computational itself. Our focus here is on three key dynamics within this becoming-operational: addressability, actionability, and intervention. *Addressability* names the work required to stabilise the relation between a symbolic regime and its physical substrate, making heterogeneous Earth systems legible to and callable by computation: aligning data formats, coordinating reference systems, establishing naming conventions and parameters, and configuring interfaces and access permissions so that elements can be queried, recombined, and acted upon across modelling and governance contexts (Dhaliwal 2022). *Actionability* refers to the tendency towards computational modelling regimes that can be taken up, adapted, and applied across contexts, producing actionable knowledge. In turn, *intervention* refers to the orientation of systems to produce outputs that circulate as decision-relevant objects—forecasts, risk surfaces, scenario comparisons, “what-if” runs—rather than remaining as isolated measurements or model artefacts. Read in this way, the computable planet is not simply an epistemic object but an infrastructural accomplishment. Computable ensembles maintain this infrastructural operativity by stabilising relations between data, models, and potential decisions, but doing so requires the ongoing management of what cannot be computed. *Incomputability* marks what cannot be fully brought under calculation at planetary scale, to which ensembles typically respond by substituting workable proxies. These proxies

include technical measures such as filling gaps and mismatches through interpolation, downscaling from the global to the local, compressing complexity through surrogate modelling, and rendering residual uncertainty as probabilistic ranges rather than resolved specificity.

Operativity is never purely technical: ensembles are sustained through industrial production, political economy, and institutional authorisation. These substitutions and stabilisations make clear why computable ensembles cannot be analysed as technical architectures alone. As Felix Guattari (1995, 48) argues, any technical machine is a conjunction composed not only of diagrammatic possibilities and material constraints, but of an industrial sector that produces it, a political economy that finances it, and a collective horizon of legitimacy that conditions its actualisation. These forces are not external to computation but conditions of its operativity. In asking what sort of object the computable Earth might be, we approach the planet less as an entity that can be seamlessly “twinned” and actioned, and more as a technical being whose computability is inseparable from the scientific, political, ecological, and epistemological trajectories in which it is entangled.

Computing Earth to Govern Earth

Humans have sought to estimate weather for millennia, but the mathematical modelling of it is often dated to Vilhelm Bjerknes’s 1904 paper *The Problem of Weather Prediction, Considered from the Viewpoints of Mechanics and Physics*, which recast meteorology as an atmospheric science. The task of turning atmospheric science into practical prediction was taken up in 1922 by Lewis Fry Richardson in *Weather Prediction by Numerical Process*, which famously imagined an army of human “computers” performing systematic calculation at scale. It was the development of electronic computation in the post-war era, however, that profoundly transformed meteorology, climate science, and Earth systems science, entangling the technical demands of prediction with the institutional and political-economic stakes of computation. As Paul Edwards (Edwards 1996) has shown, early computing’s military orientations, and especially the modelling of nuclear fallout, emerged alongside the rapid expansion of forecasting as a state and industrial priority. Emblematic of this shift were the first general circulation models (GCMs), developed by the meteorologist and computer scientist Norman Phillips at MIT in 1956, and grounded in the fluid-dynamical equations—most prominently the Navier–Stokes

equations—that formalise atmospheric and oceanic motion. Over time, these models were coupled into atmosphere–ocean general circulation models (AOGCMs), which became foundational within assessment infrastructures for projecting future warming and its impacts. From this point, the history of climate modelling becomes inseparable from the growth of coupled system complexity (atmosphere–ocean–land–ice), the escalation of computational resources needed to run ensembles at meaningful resolutions, and the institutional consolidation through which prediction is stabilised across scales in forms that can circulate as outputs useful to decision-makers.

Within the framework incrementally developed by the IPCC, atmosphere–ocean coupled general circulation models are not simply technical achievements but components of an epistemic infrastructure through which climate prediction becomes authoritative and decision-relevant. Development, application, and advancement of coupled models depends upon incremental improvement in techniques, datasets, equations, and computational schemes, typically undertaken within established modelling centres and intercomparison ecosystems (Edwards 2010). Institutions such as the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration’s Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory in the United States exemplify this mode of work: long-term investment in model development, calibration, and validation, coupled to the iterative refinement of parameterisations and the careful alignment of model outputs with observational records.² In this institutional setting, “prediction” is stabilised as a public object by producing bounded and comparable results that can be evaluated, communicated, and taken up within assessment and policy processes. Measures such as sensitivity tests and scenario projections are not about eliminating uncertainty or the incomputable but allowing prediction to account for it. Put differently, coupled models and their supporting institutions perform a translation of their own: they translate the internal operations of numerical simulation into outputs that can circulate beyond the laboratory as legible grounds for decision.

² In 2025, the second Trump administration moved to sharply scale back NOAA—most notably through a White House/OMB budget plan proposing to eliminate NOAA’s Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research (OAR) and substantially reduce NOAA funding, amid broader staffing and program cuts that observers warned would undermine weather and climate research capacity.

As Gabriele Gramelsberger (2011) explains, the production of general circulation and related climate models required translating mathematical descriptions into numerical models that could be made operable in computation. Where mathematical models can represent climate systems through differential equations, computation requires numerical models such that equations can be “solved” across a field of discrete elements. Translating from the mathematical to the numerical therefore entails modifications—“discretizations, approximations, heuristic assumptions, and other methods” (Gramelsberger 2011, 296)—through which condensed symbolic relations are converted into “innumerable instructions and computations” (2011, 301). This translation is not a straightforward mapping. It lacks a “strong isomorphism” that would allow smooth movement back and forth between measurement, mathematical model, numerical scheme, and computed prediction. The consequence is crucial for our purposes: prediction is stabilised not by mirroring Earth as it is, but by operationalising it through calculative procedures that necessarily introduce approximation, parameterisation, and scale choices (Horn and Richardson 2025; Mackenzie 2015).

What counts as a usable prediction is inseparable from scale. General circulation and coupled models have historically operated at resolutions that are appropriate to global dynamics but blunt at the scales where many impacts are felt and where most decisions are made. The demand for decision-relevant climate knowledge therefore pressures modelling systems to produce outputs that are simultaneously comparable at planetary scale and meaningful at regional and local scales. This is not a simple matter of “zooming in.” Scale is produced through modelling choices and infrastructural capacities: grid design and discretisation schemes; parameterisations that stand in for sub-grid processes; coupling strategies that align atmosphere, ocean, land, and ice components; and the ensemble practices through which results are stabilised as comparable across runs, models, and scenarios. In other words, resolution is an epistemic and infrastructural achievement tightly linked to governance contexts that demand locality: flood risk, heat stress, infrastructure planning, agriculture, shipping, and emergency response. The pressure to make predictions useful beyond climate science therefore appears as a pressure to translate between scales. Under contemporary conditions, those translation pressures intensify as machine learning is inserted into modelling pipelines, shifting how models relate to data and how uncertainty is packaged for decision.

In climate and weather modelling, machine learning is no longer confined to an instrumental role of smoothing or refining datasets prior to ingestion by established numerical models (Ferris et al. 2023; Holcomb et al. 2023). Machine learning systems trained on reanalysis data have begun to compete directly with operational numerical weather prediction in speed and accuracy. Most notable are global neural forecasting models such as GraphCast and explicitly probabilistic systems such as GenCast, as well as foundation-model approaches such as Aurora that are pretrained on large heterogeneous Earth datasets and fine-tuned for specific forecasting tasks. At the same time, machine learning is increasingly being integrated into the architecture of circulation modelling itself: hybrid “neural GCM” approaches combine differentiable solvers for large-scale dynamics with learned components for parameterised processes, with claims to generate deterministic and ensemble forecasts and even climate simulations that can compete with established physical observation models (Duan et al. 2025). These developments sharpen a central epistemological tension: whether prediction should be grounded in parameterisation of geophysical observation data and traceable model hierarchy, or in pattern recognition and learned representations whose internal operations are not straightforwardly reversible into human-legible causal structure. Balaji et al. (2022) articulate what is increasingly at stake: the demand for “traceable model hierarchy” as the condition under which prediction can remain accountable as modelling systems hybridise and accelerate. Under these conditions, the question is no longer simply how to program Earth through incrementally refined numerical schemes, but how to compute Earth through ensembles that rely on compression, surrogate substitution, and probabilistic generation to make prediction scalable, localisable, and usable in decision contexts.

A more pronounced role for machine-learning-dependent computability appears in ambitious projects to develop digital twins of planetary systems, including Destination Earth and Nvidia’s Earth-2 (built on its Omniverse platform). As Li et al (2023) argue, the promise of a “digital twin of Earth” is real-time coupling between physical and digital worlds, with interactive dashboards that integrate observations, Earth system models, and human-system data to support action on climate risks. In the terms developed in this section, this marks a shift in the product form of prediction: from model outputs oriented primarily to scientific assessment toward interfaces and workflows that package prediction as scenario products, “what-if” runs, and decision-ready

objects. At the same time, digital twins signal an inflection in modelling logics, as they increasingly rely on machine-learning operations that do not preserve the traceable isomorphisms historically sought in numerical modelling.

This incorporation of “human factors” is central to the computable planet because it reframes prediction as the basis for intervention. Li et al. propose that contemporary data analytics can integrate “hard” natural-system data with “soft” social-system data to capture human dynamics and model human–natural coevolution at planetary (X. Li et al. 2023). For our purposes, the key issue is less whether this strong form of integration can be achieved than what it does to the relation between prediction, scale, and decision. Once “human systems” become model inputs and outputs, climate prediction is re-specified as a tool for evaluating policy portfolios, investment choices, and governance interventions across scales. The epistemic question therefore shifts from how well models represent physical systems to how modelling infrastructures legitimise specific actions.

A computable planet, in this sense, is one in which incomputability is no longer encountered only as a mathematical boundary but as a practical and political problem of operativity: what must be approximated, deferred, or rendered as administrable uncertainty for prediction to circulate as decision. As modelling systems hybridise and move toward interactive, intervention-oriented forms, the stakes of those approximations rise. The question is not only what models predict, but how modelling infrastructures stabilise relations between prediction, scale, and decision. At issue here is what becomes visible and actionable, and what is obscured, excluded, or treated as acceptable loss. This is why the epistemic foundations of computable Earth ensembles matter as climate modelling becomes increasingly entangled with governance imperatives and economic logics: the forms of computation that take hold will shape not only representations of planetary futures, but the terms on which planetary systems can be acted upon through platforms such as Destination Earth.

DestinE: Concretising the Planetary

Destination Earth—marketed as DestinE—has been promoted as a flagship collaborative infrastructure to address the “challenge of adaptation to climate change,” bringing together

European institutions, scientific agencies, and private-sector providers contracted to deliver specific services and modules. Funded by the European Commission and launched in 2022, the primary partners are the European Space Agency (ESA), the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), and the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT), alongside a wider ecology of agencies and contractors. ESA is responsible for the DestinE Platform—the user-facing gateway into the broader ecosystem—which public documentation describes as “a user-friendly platform providing access to DestinE data, services and applications... built on an open, flexible, federated/scalable and secure cloud-based architecture” (European Commission n.d.). EUMETSAT operates the Data Lake, which functions as the system’s data backbone: it supports discovery and access to DestinE’s data portfolio and provides “big data” processing services designed to enable processing close to where data are produced and stored, while also linking to the high-performance computing sites used for running the digital twins (Destination Earth n.d.; EUMETSAT 2026). ECMWF, in turn, delivers the Digital Twin Engine (DTE)—the software infrastructure for extreme-scale simulation, data fusion and handling, and machine learning—and has been entrusted with producing the initial high-priority digital twins focused on Weather-Induced Extremes and Climate Change Adaptation (ECMWF, n.d.-a). These institutional roles are not merely administrative. They supply the programmatic and political-economic conditions of possibility—mandate and financing, procurement capacity, standards authority, and access to cloud/HPC infrastructures—through which DestinE can render Earth systems addressable, actionable, and decision-relevant. With initial operational phases from 2024 and a “full” digital replica of Earth promised by 2030, Destination Earth “will not only include the geophysical Earth system but also social systems global in nature” (Rothe 2024, 2). Drawing on extensive documentary and ethnographic study of its development, Delf Rothe observes that its primary goals are predictive, imagining that complex ““what-if” scenarios could be simulated with the DTE enabling not only prediction but also experimenting with the planet in a safe digital environment” (2024, 3).

For Rothe, Destination Earth constitutes a distinct form of “visual object” composed of satellite imagery, visual interfaces, marketing images, and so on, assembled with a geopolitical orientation (2024, 5–6). For Jihoon Kim (2025), it is a form of “planetary media” that collapses

together the global and planetary through logistics of optimisation and resilience. For Halpern (2025), this resilience framing mobilises longer histories of environmental, technocratic and artificial intelligence entanglements. Our concern here is with the computational apparatus of Destination Earth as a mechanism that transforms knowledge into governance action. As an assemblage of digital systems—DestinE Platform, Data Lake, Digital Twin Engine—Destination Earth shows how computational objects are composed from ensembles of multiple architectures enchainned by a shared apparatus. As technical documentation indicates, each of these core elements combine GUI and API interfaces, multimodal datasets, and cloud, machine learning and AI, and software-defined computational processes, with the Data Lake enabling multiple entry points and processing capabilities. The Digital Twin Engine extends established meteorological forecasting with machine learning to provide probabilistic projections that distribute potential weather outcomes across a curved range (ECMWF, n.d.-a). Within its Climate Change Adaptation and Weather-Induced Extremes twins, for example, the incorporation of machine learning enables predictive capacities at kilometre scales well below those of underlying Earth system models, which typically operate at lower 30-100 km resolutions.

Machine learning thereby functions as a technique for operationalising planetary models at granular levels aligned with specific regional or local challenges. Ranging from forecasting changes in Arctic seaways due to melting ice to modelling pollutants in Barcelona, DestinE's use cases position the platform as enabling not only informed policymaking across levels of governance but also economic adaptation. Read through our framework, these components do not merely 'support' modelling; they stabilise the conditions under which Earth becomes actionable. The Platform and Data Lake ensure addressability by standardising and exposing data through APIs and controlled interfaces; the DTE secures actionability by converting model outputs into scenario products and probabilistic projections; and the use-case portfolio anticipates intervention, aligning outputs with specific governance and market decisions. In this sense, DestinE operationalises the planet by assembling a pipeline in which uncertainty is rendered administrable within the system and locality is produced through machine-learning-enabled approximation. While the IPCC process incorporates human data at the global scale, this integrative approach promises to conjoin granular population, migration, social and economic

data with the environmental. That is, DestinE seeks to enact the ambition of combining “hard” and “soft” data (Li et al 2023) within an adaptive prediction platform.

Addressability is the constitutive move that anchors and enables the DestinE ensembles.

Described as a “web entry point” to data, services, and applications, the platform is built on a federated cloud architecture that connects to high-performance computing (HPC) resources and is intended to host evidence-based decision-support tools, including in the context of EU policy-making (European Commission, n.d.-a). This “entry point” is not simply a user interface, but what stabilises the ensemble. Addressability enchains what can be called and combined as “the planet” by formalising access, determining permissible queries, and coupling together various services. In the Data Lake, for instance, access is organised through protected endpoints that require registration and authentication, and a harmonised Data Access API structures search and retrieval as a standardised operation. The Data Lake also positions “processing in proximity to the data” as a key service, linking discovery and access to compute-ready workflows rather than treating data delivery as a separate step. Even at the level of user policy, DestinE differentiates categories of users and tiers of access, with the “general public” able to reach selected services after registration and other capabilities governed through upgraded access processes. Read this way, addressability is a boundary-making infrastructure: it aligns standards and interfaces with permissions and institutional mandates, thereby delimiting which Earth-system relations can be rendered interoperable, actionable, and decision-relevant within the DestinE ensemble.

Actionability is most clearly concentrated in the DTE, which is positioned as a service layer for producing outputs that can be used by policymakers, managers, bureaucrats, and other end users (Horn & Richardson 2025). It is explicitly articulated as an engine, rather than a digital twin in its own right: the software infrastructure needed to deploy and embed various Earth-system digital twins “within the overall DestinE system,” bringing together simulation, data fusion, and machine learning. The DTE functions as an operational environment designed to exploit existing HPC infrastructures and “operate the digital twins and trial on demand configurations adapted to specific applications” (European Commission, n.d.-b). Actionability figures here as an infrastructural property that orchestrates workflows so outputs can be produced as tailored simulations and what-if scenarios. For example, the Weather-Induced Extremes Digital Twin is

described as providing across past, present, and future climates, complementing existing national and European capacities (ECMWF, n.d.-b). DestinE’s “digital twins” are, in turn, characterised in terms that track our framework’s movement from model outputs to decision-relevant objects: “high-resolution information from global to local scale,” “impact sector information at relevant spatial and temporal scales,” and “interactivity” (European Commission, n.d.-b). As the ECMWF reports, downscaling via machine learning enables the Weather-Induced Extremes Digital Twin to deliver a global 4.4km resolution model at 500-700m resolution over Europe, signalling how the ensemble is engineered to deliver outputs at the scales where impacts are felt and decisions are made (ECMWF 2024). Within the ensemble, machine learning helps convert complex model fields into administrable, decision-facing forms (probabilistic projections, scenario runs, application-specific configurations) that can circulate within governance and operational planning contexts as actionable.

Intervention is clearest in the way its use-case portfolio pre-structures the planet as a set of actionable decision problems. The public use-case catalogue frames DestinE as a platform for targeted applications ranging from adaptation planning to air quality improvement to polar shipping operations. Each specifies a domain, a stakehold horizon, and a defined repertoire of possible responses. In polar contexts, DestinE use cases such as DESIDE and associated project materials foreground “decision enhancement” for sea ice and polar navigation—organising planetary change around operational risk, route planning, and the protection of sensitive areas (Destination Earth, n.d.). Within the computational ensemble framework, these are not merely illustrative “applications.” They function as an intervention grammar, or logic: they define what counts as a relevant planetary variable, the spatial and temporal scales at which it should become actionable, and the institutional actors presumed to take up outputs as grounds for action. In this sense, DestinE operationalises “the planetary” by curating the decision contexts in which Earth becomes addressable and actionable—shipping safety, air-quality measures, adaptation planning, and so on—thereby matching ensemble outputs with concrete governance decisions and actions rather than a singular, totalising image of Earth.

Yet DestinE’s operativity depends on more than orchestrating address, action, and intervention: it depends on how the ensemble handles what does not cleanly compute, whether ecological or

social. The move from heterogeneous observations and coarse global models to scenario products with value to decision-makers is sustained by the approximation inherent to machine learning. This takes place through specific techniques such as downscaling, surrogate models, gap-filling, and other substitutions that turn the rich and irreducible complexity of Earth and its ecologies into administrable uncertainty. *Incomputability* is thus as essential to the ensemble as the operative dimensions of addressability, actionability, and interventionary logic. The next section develops this concept more fully, treating incomputability as both a formal boundary and an operational remainder internal to planetary computation.

Incomputability and the Computing of Earth

Formal problems of computability theory might seem removed from planetary modelling platforms, yet they are revealing precisely because they clarify that computability is never simply given. A computable planet is assembled and maintained as an operational object only by continually negotiating the limits of what can and cannot be brought into the domain of calculation. Incomputability is not an external failure that arrives after computation has been attempted. Instead, incomputability is the constitutive twin of computation itself, antecedent to any attempt to articulate a computed planet. Faced with incomputable complexity, the ensembles of computable Earths proceed by approximation, by proxy, and by rendering uncertainty into forms that are legible to end-users in decision contexts. We thus use incomputability in three linked senses: (1) a formal boundary internal to computation; (2) a practical limit of planetary modelling; and (3) an operational remainder that ensembles redistribute as uncertainty, proxy, and acceptable loss so that decision-ready outputs can circulate.

First, we turn briefly to computability theory within formal mathematical definitions of computation (see, for example, Copeland et al. 2015). Much attention has focused on Alan Turing's 1936 thesis that all calculable functions are computable by a universal machine, crucial because it specifies a process for computability. At the same time, it delineates both what is computable (all those functions that are effectively calculable) and what is not: incomputable problems that can be approximated, rendered computable through restriction, or remain ultimately noncomputable. As Robert Soare (2007) notes, Turing's intervention delimited the boundaries of computability, formally opening computation onto what lies outside it. The key

point for our purposes is that the computable is never separable from the incomputable.

Computation proceeds under the shadow of problems and functions that fall outside its reach, and this relation is not incidental but constitutive. Incomputability is generated by, and remains internal to, the very definition of computation (Galloway 2021; Mackenzie 1996).

To see why these seemingly abstract dimensions of incomputability have practical effects, we need to delve a little further into computability theory. Kolmogorov complexity, for instance, is an attempt to measure complexity by determining the shortest program from which a file (a string x) can be reconstructed (M. Li and Vitányi 2019). Such determination must begin without knowing in advance which programs will render or “halt” on the output x and which will not. Kolmogorov complexity therefore situates quantitative compression (i.e. the shortest program) within procedural uncertainty. Even if a short program outputs a certain pattern, an even shorter program may exist, and there is no general guarantee of determining an ultimate measure of “shortness.” Kolmogorov complexity is thus a proposition not simply about computing as procedure but about information: complexity is measured by the length of the shortest program capable of reproducing an informatic object. In the context of planetary computation, this limit on definitive description sharpens the problem posed by claims to effective, efficient, and near-real-time digital twins. The question is not whether planetary systems can be modelled at all, but how “short” any adequate computational description of coupled Earth systems could be, and how one would ever know that a given modelling ecology is not both improvable and fundamentally incomplete. To be clear: we are not suggesting a direct lineage from Kolmogorov complexity to contemporary machine learning. Rather, Kolmogorov provides a language for the limits of definitive description that clarifies what is at stake when planetary computation turns to compression as a condition of operativity. Given the scale of platforms such as Destination Earth, the “shortest model” is never a single program but an ecology of models, data pipelines, and compute infrastructures, whose very composition already presupposes approximation. In this sense, incomputability is precisely the background condition that makes compression, proxy, and uncertainty management central to the making of computable Earths.

If Kolmogorov complexity clarifies the limits of definitive description, it also helps specify the practical orientation of planetary computation under constraint. In computable Earth ensembles,

the operational response is not to find the “perfect” program—a final, minimal description of Earth systems—but to adopt approximations that preserve what is useful for particular purposes, which in turn requires accepting loss, uncertainty, and incompleteness as conditions of operativity. Approximation is an enabling technique that allows models and datasets to be made workable at scale and at speed. This is one reason machine learning has become so attractive within planetary computation: it offers a family of methods for compressing complex relations into tractable representations, for substituting surrogates where computation is too costly, and for producing outputs that remain actionable even when the underlying complexity cannot be exhaustively resolved. Under these conditions, the question within emerging ensembles such as DestinE shifts from whether the planet can be computed “in full” to how approximation is organised—what is retained, what is discarded, and how uncertainty is rendered administrable so that decision-ready outputs can circulate.

If computable ensembles must proceed by compression and proxy, latent space provides a practical way of doing so: complex data are transformed into lower-dimensional representations in which similarity, relation, and variation can be manipulated without retaining all of the detail of the original domain. As Fabian Offert (2021) argues, latent space is constitutively lossy. In the case of generative models such as GANs, the “compression” of images into latent space necessarily discards features and details, and—crucially—the distribution of what is lost is not transparent. Latent representations do not simply reduce complexity; they reorganise it, redistributing what is preserved and what is discarded in ways that are often inaccessible to interpretation from the outside. Latent space is thus not a purely technical phenomenon but “a highly generative, productive and derivative space of possibilities” (Amoore et al. 2024, 4). With initiatives to compute Earth adopting machine learning techniques in different forms and degrees, the critical questions concern the political ordering of flows from latent space that constitute “the world of the model: its limitations, its possibilities, its understanding, its constraints, its potentiality, its risks, and its promissory allure” (Amoore et al. 2024, 4). Latent space functions as an operational technique for managing remainder: it makes complex worlds workable by converting irreducible detail into a space of relations that can be traversed, sampled, and optimised. Latent space does not overcome incomputability; it proceeds by accepting that exhaustive description is unavailable and instead constructing a tractable representational

substrate in which approximation can be performed. To make heterogeneous and incomplete planetary data into practical interventions, the attraction of latent representations is clear. They offer ways to gap-fill, downscale, emulate, and generate plausible outputs under constraint, while simultaneously shifting the epistemic status of model outputs from traceable derivation to the manipulation of compressed relations. The incomputable remainder is reorganised within the latent, reappearing as uncertainty, artefact, and the opaque distribution of loss that accompanies the production of actionable outputs.

Latent space marks a shift in the epistemic and political logic of planetary computability. Approximations do not merely “stand in” for a world that remains elsewhere; they participate in composing what can count as an actionable world within the ensemble. Models generate “the world of the model” through which decision-relevant reality is organised (Amoore et al. 2024, 4). In the context of DestinE, this world-making capacity is operationalised through the DTE’s orchestration of probabilistic projections, downscaling, and surrogate components that deliver outputs and scenario products at scales and resolutions that make sense within the context of governance or market decisions. Such outputs are not false but produced by redistributing remainder: converting what cannot be fully resolved into administrable uncertainty and acceptable loss so that outputs can circulate as decision objects. This returns us to incomputability in the three senses outlined at the start of the section—formal boundary, practical limit, operational remainder—while clarifying why the machine-learning turn matters for computable Earths. The next section develops these tensions further by examining how modelling systems and their infrastructures stabilise particular relations between prediction, scale, and decision, and what becomes obscured or excluded in the process.

Conclusion

What sort of thing, then, is a computable planet? It is an operational object: not a singular Earth replica, but a planet made governable by ensembles that stabilise addressability, actionability, and intervention. These ensembles hold together diverse elements—data streams, numerical models, machine-learning components, APIs, dashboards, cloud and HPC resources, and institutional mandates—so that Earth systems can be queried, recombined, and turned into

decision-facing outputs. The computable planet is a way of keeping Earth “running” as an actionable object through continual coordination and stabilisation.

DestinE offered a diagnostic gateway into this arrangement. Its platform entry points and data backbones organise interoperability and access; its digital twin engine orchestrates simulation and machine-learning extensions to generate probabilistic projections and scenario products; and its use-case portfolio anticipates intervention by prefiguring outputs in line with the demands of concrete governance processes. Yet this operativity is not secured by eliminating uncertainty. It depends on the ongoing management of limits. Incomputability appears in practice as remainder: what cannot be fully resolved at planetary scale and must be handled through approximation, proxy, and uncertainty management. The machine-learning turn intensifies this condition. Latent space compression, surrogate substitution, and probabilistic generation make prediction scalable and localisable, but they also redistribute what is preserved and what is discarded, shifting the terms on which outputs become interpretable, traceable, and actionable. As an instrument for governance, Destination Earth centres technocratic management within the bounds of the possible circumscribed by contemporary capitalism. Rather than proposing a re-arrangement of climate, planetary or even environment politics, it aims to provide tools for adapting current practices and processes for changing planetary conditions.

Intensifying the challenge is the fact that the planet being computed is not stable: in a warming world, key dynamics become increasingly variable across wider probability ranges, and the distributions on which prediction depends shift beneath the model (Munn 2023). Antarctic ice melting (Fricker et al. 2025) and Atlantic current collapse (Portmann et al. 2026) involves nonlinear thresholds and abrupt change that can rapidly reorder conditions of navigation and governance, to take two interlinked examples with planetary consequences. In such settings, computable ensembles do not so much resolve uncertainty as continually redistribute it, keeping Earth operable by converting instability into administrable risk that can be managed through proliferating model applications. Seen this way, planetary computation requires infrastructures that stabilise prediction as decision: institutional conditions under which outputs become authoritative, exclusions and externalities normalised to maintain operativity, and techniques to

convert incomputable complexity into administrable uncertainty so that model worlds can circulate as legitimate grounds for action.

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